

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Dynamic lactation responses to dietary crude protein oscillation in diets adequate and deficient in metabolizable protein in Holstein cows

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Supplementary Table 3. Body condition score regressed on experimental factors using a linear mixed model with fixed effects for cannulation status (S_j , where j = cannulated, non-cannulated), experimental period (E_k , continuous at 28-d intervals), dietary CP level (P_l , where l = LP, HP), CP feeding pattern (F_m , where m = OF, SF), and the interaction term between CP level and CP feeding pattern. We included a random intercept for and a random error term (ϵ_{ijklm} ; $n = 64$).

Fixed Effects	df	df	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
S	1	14.875	0.125	0.728
E (linear)	1	43.437	17.725	<0.001
P	1	42.929	0.644	0.427
F	1	43.557	0.068	0.796
P:F	1	42.929	1.115	0.297
Random Effects¹				
σ^2		0.02		
$\tau_{00 \text{ cow}}$		0.06		
ICC		0.81		
N_{cow}		17		
Observations		64		
Marginal R^2		0.064		
Conditional R^2		0.822		

¹The σ^2 and τ_{00} represent the within-cow and between-cow variances, respectively. ICC shows the intraclass-correlation coefficient for the random effect of cow.